

A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF UZBEK AND ENGLISH SOMATIC PROVERBS

Usmonova Umidaxon Hamzaxon qizi

Farg‘ona davlat universiteti lingvistika (ingliz tili) yo‘nalishi magistranti

usmonovaumida95@gmail.ru

Sotvaldieva Khilola Musinovna

Ferghana State University,

Senior teacher department of foreign languages for humanities

1969xilola@gmail.com

ANNOTATION

This article presents proverbial features of the somatic proverbs in both Uzbek and English. The linguistic-cultural aspect of linguistics was considered when studying the comparison of language proverbs. Paremia was highlighted as an important part of the analyzes performed.

Key words: *Paremia, proverbs, comparative research, somatism, linguoculturology, metaphor, paremiological units, lexico-thematic system, semantics, polysemy.*

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada somatik maqollarning o‘zbek va ingliz tillaridagi maqol xususiyatlari keltirilgan. Til maqollarini taqqoslashni o‘rganishda tilshunoslikning lingvistik-madaniy jihati ko‘rib chiqildi. Paremiya o‘tkazilgan tahlillarning muhim qismi sifatida ta’kidlandi.

Kalit so‘zlar: *paremiya, maqollar, qiyosiy tadqiqotlar, somatizm, lingvokulturologiya, metafora, paremiologik birliklar, leksiko-tematik tizim, semantika, polisemiya.*

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье представлены пословичные особенности соматических пословиц как в узбекском, так и в английском языках. Лингвокультурологический аспект лингвистики рассматривался при изучении сопоставления языковых пословиц. Паремии были выделены в качестве важной части проведенных анализов.

Ключевые слова: паремия, пословицы, сравнительное исследование, соматизм, лингвокультурология, метафора, паремиологические единицы, лексико-тематическая система, семантика, многозначность.

A saying or proverb is a type of saying that contains advice or simply contains truth or other universal values. This is a popular short sentence where people use proverbs to express their feelings. A proverb can say much more than a thousand words. Morality, truth, wisdom, friendship, loyalty, etc. are values that are celebrated using these sayings. Proverbs can be used orally and in writing in a literal or figurative sense.

Some proverbs are only used figuratively ("Qarg'a qarg'aning ko'zini cho'qimaydi" ("A crow never pecks a crow's eye"), "Quruq qoshiq og'iz yirtar" ("Empty hands are no bait"). hawks")) or literally ("Ona yurtning omon bolsa, rangiro-roying somon bolmas" ("If your country is doing well, you are doing well"). there is")).

Proverbs are rich and varied in terms of the subject matter used. There are proverbs on themes such as Motherland, Work, Knowledge, Skills, Friendship, Unity, Wisdom, Vigilance, Language and Language Culture, Love, Bad Nature, etc. Typical characteristics of proverbs are: dialectical unity of content and form; sometimes the rhyme is rich; it can have many meanings; they are metaphorical. In proverbs, we often find such phenomena as antitheses (e.g., "Kattaga hurmatda bol, kichikka izzatda" ("Honor the elder, honor the younger")). Proverbs can also be prose and poetic. The prose contains proverbs like "Mehnat, mehnatning tagi rohat" ("Work is over, time to have fun"), but the motif is still poetic. Like the poem, "Elga bersang oshigni, ellar

silar boshingni. Itga bersang oshigni, itlar g‘ajir boshingni"(Give your food to dogs and they will nibble on your head. ”)

The following proverb is popular among the people."Qil uchida turibman" ("I am hanging in limbo", "Semizlinki qo‘y ko‘taradi" ("Fat is good for a ram"), "Tuyaga yantoq kerak bolsa, boynini chozar" ("If If you need a camel") bur, it stretches its neck"), "Bekorga Mushuk Ofobga Chiqmaydi" ("No cat comes out without a reason").

Proverb is a short saying that expresses truth or a little useful wisdom is. Usually, it is based on common sense. The effect of a proverb is to make the wisdom it conveys self-evident. The same proverb is often seen among several different people.

Proverbs have always been the most active and at the same time the most stable part of the national language, able to compete with the proverbs and aphorisms of good thinkers. The peculiarity of thought was expressed. Proverbs and proverbs are short but deeply meaningful papers of folklore. They express the point of view of a crowd of people through their social and ideal functions. The proverbs and proverbs themselves contain certain characteristics of the historical development and culture of the people.

Somatic vocabulary (from Greek ‘‘soma’’ to ‘‘body’’) - one of the lexical groups of all languages and the most common research object in the comparative historical and linguistic-cultural studies of national and international linguists. , usually stressing this vocabulary first. Vocabulary - the subject system of any language. Somatic - a noun that has the original meaning of a part of the human or animal body. Body vocabulary means units whose constituents are words - the names of parts of the human body, animal bodies.

The term can be used in biology, medicine. In the late 20th and early 21st centuries, linguists have paid special attention to body vocabulary, seeking to find tolerant solutions to the problem of intercultural communication and to enhance the effectiveness of studying the lexical composition of languages. This term was first introduced by the oldest layers of phraseology and represents the most commonly used vocabulary of all terms. It is actively used in the study of words that mean things.

The linguist's interest in somaticity begins with the sensations that arise from the sensations and parts of one's body, the process of recognizing oneself as a person, a person began with sensations that arise through the senses and parts of his own body. "A person is egocentric, - writes V.G. Gak in one of his last works - he sees in himself the center of the universe and displays the world in its own likeness nationality, can such parts of your body as head, leg, eye, ear, and so on. Somaticity represents a set of concepts and relationships necessary for human society, without which human language is difficult to imagine, and somatic vocabulary is frequently used and characterized by well-developed polysemy. Somatic vocabulary is a holistic system that has a fixed number of objects of nominations and aims to specify a particular configuration of lexical items. The first indicator is non-verbal that relate to the actual reality in which languages develop and function, regardless of national language, and those that relate directly to the individual characteristics of a particular language.

The composition, corresponding lexemes, can differ both quantitatively and qualitatively. The heart is the primary and central organ of humans. A person's inner world is always centered on the mind. In Uzbek and English paralysis, this physicalism most often symbolizes human emotions such as experience, joy, love, and sadness.

The most basic are the values shown below.

Heart

1) A hollow muscular organ that pumps blood through the circulatory system by rhythmic contraction and expansion.

2) The mind is considered to be the center of a person's thoughts and feelings, especially love and compassion.

3) The center or innermost part of something.

After examining these values, we can conclude that the English and Uzbek definitions are consistent with each other. I analyzed some Uzbek and English proverbs. In Uzbek, 'heart' is used in 12 proverbs with the main meaning, which is 21%, and in English it is 27% in 12 proverbs. It turns out that in Uzbek Paremia, the heart is defined in its original sense by adjectives such as painful (1), human (1), hawk

(1), and sick (1). In English paremiology, lexeme heart is defined by adjectives such as human (2) - human, big (1) - big, thick (1) - thick, stout (1) - strong.

Proverbs are a genre of oral folk art. It is a wise word for short, figuratively, grammatically and logically complete sentences with deep meaning. Proverbs reflect observations relevant to people's lives, attitudes towards society, history, mental states, ethical and aesthetic sensibilities, and positive qualities. After being preserved by people for many centuries, they became a laconic and simple poetic form.

REFERENCES

1. Sotvaldieva, H. M. (2021). Using proverbs as A lead-In activity in teaching english as A Foreign Language. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research*, 10(11), 159-163.
2. Sotvaldieva, H. M. (2020). ENGLISH PROVERBS AS A MEANS OF EXPRESSING PEOPLE'S WISDOM, SPIRIT AND NATIONAL MENTALITY. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (2), 601-604.
3. Porubay, I. F., & Sotvaldieva, H. M. (2022). ANALYSIS OF IT-RELATED LEXICON AND INTERNET COMMUNICATION. *Thematics Journal of English Language Teaching*, 6(1).
4. Сотвалдиева, Х. М., & Машарипова, А. Т. (2022). ОБУЧЕНИЕ ЧЕРЕЗ ПОСЛОВИЦЫ. In *НАУКА И ПРОСВЕЩЕНИЕ: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ, ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ* (pp. 135-136).
5. Musinovna, S. H., & Tadjibaevn, M. A. (2021). STRUCTURAL AND SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS OF PROVERBS. *Евразийский Союз Ученых*, (1-4 (82)), 22-25.
6. Sotvaldieva, K., & Toshmirzayeva, D. (2022). COGNITIVE STUDY OF "HAPPINESS" METAPHORS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK IDIOMS. *Science and innovation*, 1(B6), 914-919.
7. Musinovna, S. H., & Mirxamidovna, M. G. (2022). Paremiological Units in Uzbek, English and Russian. *International Journal of Formal Education*, 1(10), 18-21.
8. Сотвалдиева, Х. М., & Машарипова, А. Т. (2022). ОБУЧЕНИЕ ЧЕРЕЗ ПОСЛОВИЦЫ. In *НАУКА И ПРОСВЕЩЕНИЕ: АКТУАЛЬНЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ, ДОСТИЖЕНИЯ И ИННОВАЦИИ* (pp. 135-136).